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Sectoral investments to achieve water, energy and land SDG under climate change uncertainty

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Abstract

Achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGs) requires a deep understanding of the intricate relationships between water, energy, food, and land resources, particularly in the context of a growing global population and climate change. Previous studies have either explored individual SDG investment needs or analyzed climate impacts independently, but few have integrated these aspects across multiple sectors. This paper addresses this gap by exploring how climate impacts alter investment needs for key SDGs related to water, energy, and food security, using the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM-Nexus model to analyze optimal multi-sector investment strategies. By comparing scenarios with and without SDG targets and climate impacts based on radiative concentration pathway 6.0 forcing, and across different water availability assumptions, we identify regions with the highest uncertainties in development costs due to climate change. Developing countries in Asia and sub-Saharan Africa will need to increase their spending by 10%–30%, compared to current trends, to meet their SDGs for water. Climate-related uncertainties lead to a spread in investment needs of 30% in the water sector and 5% in the energy sector in the most affected regions, amounting to billions of dollars. Our findings show that cross-sectoral policies, such as those aimed at reducing food waste and improving nutrition, can yield significant cost savings by reducing water demand, especially in water-scarce regions such as South Asia. The study also highlights the importance of considering long-term costs and uncertainties to maintain the standards of SDG targets throughout the century, with large variations in expected investment requirements in Asia under climate change scenarios after 2040. The study provides a framework for understanding the economic implications of climate impacts on SDG achievement and highlights the need for dedicated financing strategies that incorporate resilience in development finance.

List of abbreviations

SDG	Sustainable development goal
WEL	Water energy and land
IAM	Integrated assessment model
SSP	Shared socioeconomic pathways
RCP	Radiative concentration pathways, determining level of CO ₂ emission concentration in the atmosphere over time
COP	Conference of the Parties organized by the UNFCCC
WASH	It is a UNICEF program to provide water access, sanitation and hygiene services.
AAIOM	Annual Average Investments and Operational and Management cost
O&M	Operational and Management costs

1. Introduction

In the pursuit of the SDGs mapped by the UN in 2015 (UN 2015) water, energy, food, and land resources are critical and tightly interlinked focal points, fundamental for basic human needs and development, whilst also linked to the planetary boundaries (Howells *et al* 2013, Biggs *et al* 2015, Khan *et al* 2017, McCollum *et al* 2018a, Wackernagel *et al* 2021). The SDGs address a wide array of socio-economic and environmental targets, from energy and food security to climate action and responsible resource management. Achieving individual SDGs in isolation can lead to unintended consequences, potentially undermining other goals. For example, pursuing climate change mitigation through large-scale bioenergy deployment could negatively impact food security and biodiversity (Doelman *et al* 2022). Conversely, actions can create synergistic benefits, such as expanding electricity access in Sub-Saharan Africa, which can boost agricultural development and water access (Falchetta *et al* 2022). A nexus approach focusing on the water, energy, land and climate (WC) nexus, is crucial for understanding key interlinkages and identifying potential synergies and trade-offs (Fader *et al* 2018, Khan *et al* 2022).

With a growing global population and increasing climate pressures on resources, addressing the interactions between these essential policy goals has become critical for ensuring a climate-resilient and equitable future (Rasul and Sharma 2016, Mpandeli *et al* 2018).

Ten years after the mapping of the SDGs, development gaps remain large in several countries—meaning that millions of people lack access to basic services—and international investment in development has slowed, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine, which led, along with direct and indirect greenhouse gas emissions, to disruptions in energy and food supply chains and trade, infrastructure planning, and investment flows (Arora and Sarker 2023). Policy responses to these crises and other wars around the world have often prioritized rapid economic recovery over long-term sustainability (Aday and Aday 2020, Sun *et al* 2024).

Financing the SDGs is crucial to bridging investment gaps and fostering long-term sustainability, yet it is not without risks. The nature of financing schemes might be different across sectors. For instance, irrigation technologies, as well as off-grid electricity applications, might be easier to capitalize compared to large water investments, which present unique challenges due to high capital costs, long payback periods, and regulatory complexities (Zhan and Santos-Paulino 2021). Unlike other infrastructure sectors, water investments often require sustained public support and governance reforms to attract private capital (Jiang and Yong Jiang 2023). Still, water access and regulation are key for planning agriculture, indicating that the financing plans should have a multi-sector perspective. Addressing these challenges requires innovative financial mechanisms that balance returns with affordability and long-term sustainability (Bloomberg *et al* 2017).

At the same time, climate change already shows its effects in terms of mean temperature and water availability, affecting crop yields, water and food provision and needs (Immerzeel *et al* 2010, Lutz *et al* 2016, Jägermeyr *et al* 2021, Denissen *et al* 2022, Awais *et al* 2024). The energy sector is also affected by global and regional mean temperature changes, with variations in demand (for example, room cooling need) and changes to water availability for hydropower or cooling systems of thermal power plants (van Vliet *et al* 2016, Sridharan *et al* 2019, Gernaat *et al* 2021, Mastrucci *et al* 2022).

More broadly, several studies have estimated macroeconomic losses under higher levels of global warming, with projections reaching double-digit losses—up to 40% of GDP by 2050 compared to a no-warming scenario (Burke *et al* 2018, Kotz *et al* 2024). In all cases, the most severe impacts are projected for countries in the Global Majority. However, these analyses lack sectoral granularity, making it difficult to directly connect economic losses to specific investment needs in the WEL sectors. (Sánchez 2018).

Climate change exacerbates global and regional inequalities, disproportionately affecting countries with the least responsibility for emissions and the lowest capacity to adapt (Byers *et al* 2018, Pachauri *et al* 2022, Andrijevic *et al* 2023). Some regional case studies focus on development needs, the capacity to adapt to climate change and cooperation as a strategy to tackle these challenges in cross-boundary basins (Vinca *et al* 2020, Basheer *et al* 2023).

The focus on climate impacts led the international community to set the need to finance adaptation at the COP7 as part of the Kyoto Protocol. However, for developing countries adaptation often blurs with sustainable and resilient development, funded by parallel finances from the United Nations Development Program. Having separate financing streams for adaptation and development might lead to definition barriers, complications, and low disbursement rates for developing countries to receive funding. (World Bank 2019, UNEP 2023).

The UN Trade and Development estimates an SDG investment gap of more than \$4 trillion in 2023, with energy (including mitigation investments) and water playing the lion's share. This number is gathered from different single-SDG studies. However, it does not take into account sectoral interactions, possible economic synergies or trade-offs (UNCTAD 2023).

Other sectoral studies have assessed the investment requirements for achieving the SDGs related to energy for adapting to heat stress and for curtailing emissions (McCollum *et al* 2018b, Mastrucci *et al* 2021), and water access, sanitation and fighting hunger (Parkinson *et al* 2019, Doelman *et al* 2022, Kulkarni *et al* 2022), as well as maintaining the ecosystem, often using IAMs with explicit representation of the energy sectors, water infrastructure and land and agriculture systems to study long-term development scenarios (Khan *et al* 2017, van Soest *et al* 2019, Soergel *et al* 2021, van Vuuren *et al* 2022).

Kulkarni *et al* (2022) present a comprehensive overview of such studies that assess global SDG investment needs per sector, highlighting a wide range of uncertainty. The water sector needs range from tens of billions to approximately 560 billion USD to achieve the WASH goals (Kulkarni *et al* 2022). A similar outcome limited to Asia emerges from Borgomeo *et al* (2023), where continental annual water investment needs are estimated to be between 120–330 billion USD by 2030 instead of the current 40–50 billion USD (Borgomeo *et al* 2023).

While the costs of providing electricity access in Sub-Saharan Africa are estimated to be below 20 billion USD for a decade of investments (Valickova and Elms 2021), Kulkarni *et al* show higher global numbers, up to 300 billion USD that also include energy efficiency goals, highlighting the overlap in accounting for SDG 13 (climate) when considering investments in renewable energy.

Despite the recognized importance of integrated development and climate strategies, existing literature often assesses SDG investment needs and climate impacts separately, without quantifying how climate change affects the cost of meeting development targets. This paper addresses that gap by exploring how climate impacts alter investment needs for key SDGs related to water, energy, and food security. While regional SDG investment needs have been disclosed in the literature, we want to identify regions with the highest development cost uncertainties due to climate change to increase awareness of the need for dedicated financing strategies.

Unlike previous studies focused on SDG investment needs or quantified climate impacts, our research integrates these dimensions within an IAM framework to provide a comprehensive understanding of their interactions. By incorporating direct sectoral biophysical climate impacts into the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM-Nexus IAM, we investigate the interplay between climate change impacts and SDG achievement investment and operational costs in the water and energy sectors. The model explicitly represents the global water, energy, and land sectors in an internally consistent optimization framework. Unlike simpler economic models, it captures feedbacks between resource availability, demand shifts, and sector-specific technological and policy interventions (Fricko *et al* 2017). This approach enables a more precise estimation of how climate impacts influence SDG investment pathways while ensuring consistency with long-term mitigation and adaptation goals. The multi-sector approach allows capturing cross-sector interaction both concerning policies and climate impacts, while sector-specific policies risk overlooking important cross-sectoral synergies and trade-offs (Liu *et al* 2018).

This model has been developed to have a broad policy scope. It has been used to explore synergies between mitigation policies and SDG policies (Schmidt Tagomori *et al* 2024), to understand climate impacts, to compare adaptation and resilience policies with mitigation (Awais *et al* in review), or, in this case, to explore SDG investment needs under climate uncertainty.

Particular focus is given to a set of sectoral SDG targets, such as providing cooling to the heat-exposed share of the population; full electricity, clean water and sanitation access; halving food waste by 2030, gradual shift to a healthy Lancet diet and nutrition level and conservation of about 30% of global protected land (more detail in [Methods](#), table 1). These targets differ sometimes from the original SDG idea of having 2030 as a strict deadline, to reflect feasibility constraints as defined in van Vuuren 2022 (Mustajoki *et al* 2022, van Vuuren *et al* 2022).

The success and the effort involved in achieving such policy goals are likely to be affected by changes in mean and peak temperatures, precipitation patterns, atmosphere and biosphere interrelation (e.g. CO₂ fertilization). Therefore, we implemented direct sectoral climate impacts in the model and related adaptation strategies, such as the additional energy demand for universal access to cooling services (e.g. air conditioning), water availability, and changes in crop yields and water requirements (see [Methods](#) and table 1). With this framework, we can explore the SDG pathways with different levels of climate impacts and uncertainty and their corresponding investment and O&M.

This study advances existing SDG investment research by explicitly integrating climate impact uncertainties into sectoral investment pathways and accounting for the climate uncertainty. We show how the water and energy investment requirements to achieve some sectoral SDGs vary by up to 5% in the energy sector and even 30% in the water sector when taking into account climate impact uncertainty because of system adaptation. By integrating biophysical sectoral climate impacts into economic assessments, we reveal both the cross-sectoral economic benefits in the water sector of achieving land-related SDG targets, and the

Table 1. SDG policy and climate impacts implementation in the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM. Adapted from Awais *et al* (2024). CC BY 4.0.

Sectors	SDG measures	Biophysical climate impacts
Water (SDG6)	<p>Efficiency improvement for irrigation: Limited irrigation water consumption in agriculture to sustainable removal rates that do not jeopardize ecosystem services and environmental flows (Frank <i>et al</i> 2021)</p> <p>Efficiency improvement for electric power generation and industry: General efficiency improvement in piped water distribution efficiency by 10%, as higher maintenance costs</p> <p>Implement environmental flow constraints. Based on the variable monthly flow (VMF) method developed by (Pastor <i>et al</i> 2014, Pastor <i>et al</i> 2019) where 60% and 30% of the mean monthly natural flow is reserved for ecosystems in low and high flow periods, respectively.</p> <p>Universal piped water access, wastewater collection and improved wastewater treatment capacity. Minimum of half of all return flows are treated by 2030 for developed regions and 2040 for developing regions.</p>	<p>Water availability Runoff and groundwater recharge from CWatM calculated at 0.5×0.5 grid (Burek <i>et al</i> 2019).</p> <p>Desalination potential Desalination potential climate impacts are based on water stress outputs from the combinations of GHMs & GCMs from (Byers <i>et al</i> 2018)</p>
Energy (SDG7)	<p>Maximized electricity access Results from the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM are iterated through the MESSAGE-Access-E-USE (end-use services of energy) model by provision of access targets based on income levels and GDP pathways and population with access to modern energy access and the energy demand adjustments are calculated.</p> <p>Minimized traditional bio and coal in cooking and heating 90% access target to modern cooking energy for cooking by 2030</p> <p>Heating/cooling demand closing AC cooling demand gap</p>	<p>Renewable supply (hydro) Hydropower costs supply curves based on 0.5×0.5 grid calculations (Gernaat <i>et al</i> 2021)</p> <p>Thermal power plants' cooling capacity factor Climate impacts on cooling water discharges for cooling technologies of fossil power plants are used from (Yalew <i>et al</i> 2020)</p> <p>Heating/cooling demand Impact via population-weighted heating and cooling demands based on the work of 0.5×0.5 grid (Byers <i>et al</i> 2018, Mastrucci <i>et al</i> 2021).</p>
Food (SDG2—Hunger)	<p>Change towards a healthy diet. <1% undernourishment goal by 2030 Decrease of animal calorie intake to 430 kcal/capita/day by 2030 (USDA recommendations for healthy diets)</p> <p>Reduce food waste. 50% reduction in food waste by 2030 compared to SSP2 assumptions</p>	
Land (SDG15—Life on land)	<p>Implement protected land maps Based on (Frank <i>et al</i> 2021) 34% protection in 2030 was assumed and additional area based on the UNEP- WCMC Carbon and Biodiversity Report to identify highly biodiverse areas and prevent their conversion to agriculture or forest management from 2030 onwards.</p>	<p>Crop yields (excluded) Climate impacts on crop productivity, nitrogen, and irrigation from the CMIP6 projections of the crop-model EPIC-IIASA are used in GLOBIOM.</p>

potential challenges posed by climate uncertainties, especially in water-scarce regions. Notably, while most of the SDG literature is oriented on the short term, our findings highlight the need for long-term planning and resilience-building measures in water infrastructure to address the increasing frequency of extreme climate events.

2. Methods

In this study, we use the global IAM MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM (Krey *et al* 2020), which is an energy-economic-agricultural-land use framework that evaluates the interconnected global energy systems, agriculture, land use, climate, and the economy. The MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM framework has been widely used to study the cost-effectiveness of climate policies in the context of previous IPCC Assessment Reports, to explore SDG goals in the energy and water sectors, and to analyze the feasibility of attaining global climate targets while preserving food security (McCollum *et al* 2018a, Parkinson *et al* 2019, Riahi *et al* 2021, Kikstra *et al* 2022).

This framework integrates various elements that allow flexible linking across sectors as shown by the diagram in (figure 1). For this study the energy model MESSAGEix (Huppmann *et al* 2019) is linked with the aggregated macro-economic model MACRO (Messner and Schrattenholzer 2000), which captures GDP and energy demand responses, and with the land use model GLOBIOM (Havlík *et al* 2014), with a representation of land-use, and agriculture and food production. MESSAGEix also includes different sub-sectoral modules, we use the MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM-Nexus module (Awais *et al* 2024), which endogenizes water allocation decisions and links WEL climate impacts as well as important SDG targets across sectors. While the MESSAGEix energy sector is resolved at a macro-region level (as in figures 3(b) and (c)), the Nexus module includes the representation of water infrastructure at the hydrological basin spatial level, mapping the MESSAGEix macro-region to 210 river basins globally.

A major asset of the framework is the ability to simulate global interactions across many sectors and allow the study of policies—translated in the model as assumptions and constraints—as well as different socioeconomic narratives SSPs and climate scenarios framed by the RCPs (van Vuuren *et al* 2011, Riahi *et al* 2017).

The model runs optimization algorithms that minimize total global system costs in a perfect foresight process until the end of the time horizon in 2100. This might differ from real-world situations where inefficiency, instability and inertia might make decisions and investments not as rational and cost-optimal as in the model. It is important to be aware of it and consider model outcomes, especially costs, as an optimistic proxy and a lower estimate for real applications. The optimization considers scenario-specific demand (e.g. electricity, heat, water, food demands) and sectoral constraints, such as limits to fossil fuels' potential or water availability. SDG targets, as well as climate impacts, are defined in the model as sectoral constraints in

the forms of upper or lower limits, or target shares of resource use. The time resolution of the model is defined in 5 year time steps from 2020 to 2060 and 10 year steps until 2100.

The integrated approach thoroughly considers the trade-offs and synergies between diverse policy objectives, such as increasing space cooling and water access, enhancing food security, and protecting natural resources. In the context of sustainable development, it can analyze the viability and implications of various policy alternatives and inform decision-making. In the case of climate impacts, it shows how the system (e.g. installed capacity of power technologies or water supply) could change, shaping cost-minimized adaptation. The model core formulation is explained in the MESSAGEix documentation³ while an explanation of the global application of MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM has a detailed, separated documentation⁴.

2.1. WEL SDGs

Table 1 shows the SDG targets considered in this study and how they are implemented in MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM.

Concerning the food-related SDG, the GLOBIOM model has constraints that measure and limit undernourishment below 1% globally in 2030. The diets around the globe are assumed to decrease animal calorie intake compared to current levels. Constraints to protect land use are also implemented based on (Frank *et al* 2021).

In the water sector, there are efficiency improvement assumptions in irrigation and piped distribution systems, increased rates of water treatment and recycling compared to current trend projections, and constraints in the use of natural blue water resources to maintain sustainable levels of environmental flows.

Cooling thermal demand is also a variable that we look at in the energy sector and the SDG target aims at meeting demands that are currently unmet through increased air conditioning. To assess the theoretical gap in the population with basic access to electricity and basic cooling, we use the MESSAGE-ACCESS model. This is however not endogenized in MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM and does not affect the demand in the energy balance. Therefore, we do not assess here the cost or the energy needs to achieve full energy access, but the tool is used for post-process accounting for the expected number of people with access to electricity for each scenario.

Importantly, the advantage of using integrated multi-sector models such as MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM is that cross-sectoral impacts of policies in a specific sector are taken into account. An example is the increase in electricity consumption due to more water treatment or advanced irrigation technologies, which reduce water withdrawals.

2.2. Climate impacts

The literature is divided into major approaches for assessing and modelling climate impacts on the economy and individual sectors. Piontek *et al* (2021) describe different methods to assess economic impacts either studying historical GDP and climate (e.g. temperature increase) trends with econometric approaches (top-down) or starting from biophysical impacts in process-based or statistical models (bottom-up, Piontek *et al* 2021). Often IAMs are used to aggregate impacts and estimate the effects on growth (Drouet *et al* 2021). One limitation of general-equilibrium economic approaches is that often they lack sectoral detail (Sánchez 2018).

Other bottom-up approaches do not look at the overall economic impact, but rather focus on sectoral implications, such as demand for ambient cooling to face heat waves or changes in power plant potential (Gernaat *et al* 2021, Mastrucci *et al* 2021, Zapata *et al* 2022). These methods usually use highly technical sectoral models and are not linked to integrated frameworks, which makes their outcome little comparable to other estimates.

Still, researchers so far struggle to combine SDG and mitigation analysis with climate impact assessment in process-based IAMs, because of the foreseeable large complexity and uncertainty in representing impacts across all sectors (Khan *et al* 2017, van Soest *et al* 2019, Piontek *et al* 2021). The development of Climate Impact Models, with high spatial and temporal resolution and highly detailed biophysical interactions between atmosphere, land, and water, has made these tools useful and complementary to IAMs in studying climate policy implications (Nozaki *et al* 2023, van Maanen *et al* 2023).

In this study, we explore how biophysical climate impacts in the water and energy sectors affect the investment and operational costs to achieve the aforementioned SDG targets.

Table 1 also includes the impacts included in MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM, which are explained in detail in (Awais *et al* 2024).

³ MESSAGEix documentation: <https://docs.messageix.org/en/latest/index.html>.

⁴ MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM documentation: <https://docs.messageix.org/projects/models/en/latest/water/index.html>.

The main drivers of impacts in the water, energy and land sectors are changes in air temperatures (average and peak) and precipitation patterns. These factors impact the availability of blue water resources, including river runoff and groundwater recharge, which we refer to as renewable freshwater. We use surface and groundwater availability monthly projections from the Global hydrological Model CWatM (Burek *et al* 2019), which run with bias-corrected meteorological forcing data from three different climate models GFDL-ESM2M, HadGEM2-ES, IPSLCM5A-LR. This data, available through the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project ISIMIP3 database, CMIP6 run cycle, is aggregated in timeseries for the RCP 6.0 scenario at the 50th, 70th and 90th percentile 30 year water availability to respectively define the *low-, medium- and high-reliability* scenarios (table S2). The *low-reliability* scenario assumes average annual runoff (50th percentile) and may overestimate water availability during drier seasons, making it relatively optimistic. Conversely, the *high-reliability* scenario uses the 90th percentile to ensure the water system's resilience to low runoff conditions, reflecting investment needs for stable water access.

The RCP 6.0 future climate assumption is likely to be consistent with the so-called 'current policy' future, where countries do not pursue additional climate mitigation effort beyond the existing ongoing policies throughout the 21st century (Kikstra *et al* 2022). However, different climate assumptions should be explored to cover several areas of uncertainty, such as future socioeconomic development, climate models' variability, the coarse spatial and temporal resolution of IAM, and more.

Water availability, together with air temperature affects the hydropower available future potential and its cost, as well as the capacity factor of thermoelectric power plants (e.g. coal, gas, and nuclear plants) that rely on water cooling systems such as once-through and closed-loop.

Desalination potential and need, which are dependent on socio-economic conditions, are likely to change with increasing water stress, we define this potential in the model as an upper boundary to the possibility of expanding desalination.

Rising air temperature and heat waves are likely to increase the share of the global population exposed to extreme heat, consequently heightening cooling demand in commercial and domestic buildings, which we account for in MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM.

Climate impacts on the land sector are driven by changes in precipitation patterns, evapotranspiration of plants influenced by temperature, humidity change and CO₂ fertilization (the effect of the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere that impacts the photosynthesis and the yield of plants).

Estimation and changes in crop yields for the RCP 6.0 are included in the GLOBIOM emulator in our framework. However, by comparing the impacted crop yields from GLOBIOM with the IMAGE 3.2 IAM and with values present in recent literature (Jägermeyr *et al* 2021), we noticed that GLOBIOM results diverge from other estimates when aggregated at the macro-region. Given the large ranges of uncertainty in yield estimates, we created scenarios that exclude the impacts on the crop yields, denoted by the *noland* tag in the scenario name.

2.3. Scenarios and input data

Combining the different policy and climate settings, we define a set of 27 scenarios mapped in table S2. Twelve scenarios do not consider any SDG target. Three of these explore a future without changing climate forcing (*noSDG-rcpref*) at different water reliability levels (high is the default, *lowrel* and *medrel* for low and medium reliability respectively). Six scenarios consider climate impacts corresponding to the RCP6.0 temperature trend for all the WEL sectors, or excluding the land impacts, by three water reliability levels. The remaining three scenarios explore the single sectoral impacts at high-reliability confidence.

This set of scenarios allows us to isolate the effects of climate forcing in different sectors in the absence of SDG policies. Since we are mostly interested in the interplay between climate and SDG investments, we replicate the just mentioned scenario logic by adding all SDG targets as objectives in the model for different climate assumptions (e.g. *SDG-rcpref* and *SDG-rcp6p0-lowrel*).

In addition, we add scenarios where the single individual SDG is set with or without the corresponding sectoral climate impact (e.g. *SDG-wat-rcp6p0-wat*) for sensitivity analysis.

Awais *et al* (2024) describe in detail these and additional scenarios, mentioning the data sources required to parametrize the model. Given the broad spectrum of input data to represent technologies, policy targets and climate impacts in multiple sectors, the development was limited to exploring only one RCP scenario. Future work will try to automate part of the input data processing to facilitate the testing of different climate-forcing assumptions.

2.4. Investment assessment

MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM is a dynamic optimization capacity expansion model. The decision variables of the model are whether to build certain technologies (which can be real technologies or fictitious, like a crop field) and how much to use them for 1 year, considering space and time dimensions. Most technologies have

unit capital investment costs (e.g. \$/kW for power plants) and costs for O&M, associated with their use (e.g. \$/kWh for producing energy). For a full understanding of the model equations, we invite the reader to the online model documentation⁵. For comparison purposes, we converted the monetary unit to USD 2010 Purchasing Power Parity.

The model provides annual investment and O&M costs for each region or river basin based on the resulting capacity and use of technologies. Given the long lifespan of technologies, investment flows tend to vary considerably over time. Therefore, we analyze and present the results looking at annual averages for specific time-horizons. To focus on short-term SDG requirements and long-term climate impacts we consider here two timeframes, namely *short-term* between 2020–2040 and *long-term*, between 2045–2100.

In this manuscript, we refer to AAIOM cost to achieve the water, energy and land-related SDGs calculated as the difference between scenarios with SDG targets to those where such targets are not implemented, given the same climate assumptions. For instance, for the scenarios with historical climate and high water reliability, the SDG AAIOM is calculated as the cost difference between *SDG_rcpref* and *noSDG_rcpref*. In a RCP6.0 and low-reliability case, it would be between *SDG_rcp6p0_low* and *noSDG_rcp6p0_low*.

Due to structural constraints, the bottom-up, technology-based cost assessment of MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM only covers the energy supply and the whole water system infrastructure (e.g. pumping, distribution, irrigation, etc.), but possible investments in the energy demand (e.g. building refurbishing, cost of policy implementations) and the land sector (machinery, processing, transporting, etc.) are not included.

Given the limitation of not accounting for investments in the land sector common in other similar IAMs like IMAGE 3.2, our focus is mainly on the water and energy sector costs (Frank *et al* 2021, Doelman *et al* 2022).

3. Results

3.1. Investment uncertainty compared with the literature

Figure 2(a) shows the annual average investment and O&M costs in energy supply and water infrastructure to achieve the water, energy, food and biodiversity SDGs resulting from MESSAGEix-GLOBIOM-Nexus and compared with literature estimates in Kulkarni *et al* (2022).

The reported cost for SDG7* from MESSAGEix only refers to the additional supply capacity needed to fulfill the energy demand in the residential and commercial cooling sector, which results in just 6% of the maximum total SDG7 costs estimated from the literature mentioned in Kulkarni *et al* (2022). This latter cost includes, however, additional demand-side investments and O&M costs related to achieving full electrification, switching heating and cooking to electric globally.

Concerning SDG 6 (water) the model estimate is directly comparable with the literature in terms of cost coverage. The paper of Kulkarni *et al* shows biased results in two major uncertainty areas. Our results fall within the lowest range and estimate between 47 and 76 billion USD/year in annual average investment and O&M. This only refers to the additional investments needed to achieve the SDG and not the total water investments, which is around 350–400 billion USD/year (figure 3(a)).

Importantly, we notice the annual average cost to be higher in the long-term, up to a maximum of 128 billion USD/year, rather than in the period usually framed by the SDGs. In our SDG scenarios, we estimate that 612 million additional people will gain access to drinking water by 2040 (see (Awais *et al* 2024) for details on the assessment) and what makes the difference in investments and O&M is the need to maintain the additional infrastructure for the rest of the century (see figure S4).

Achieving the food and land SDG targets (SDG 2 and 15) leads to 13–26 billion USD/year reductions in model-based energy supply and water infrastructure investment and O&M, as shown in figure 2(b). This synergetic saving is mainly driven by an important reduction in water withdrawals in agriculture due to the food waste reduction goal, even if in some regions this is compensated by increased production to achieve higher nutrition standards defined with the EAT-Lancet diet (Willett *et al* 2019). Regions like Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia have almost no reduction or even increase in overall food crop and livestock demand. However, the global average demand decreases, in some cases, thanks to a broader use of fertilizer (e.g. India). This determines important reductions in water withdrawals and annual average investments (figures S2 and S3). South East Asia and India in particular would largely benefit from the global food demand reduction, with reduced demand for water investment of about 18%, followed by China with 6%.

⁵ <https://docs.messageix.org/en/latest/>.

The SDGs 2 and 15 also come at some costs and, while our model does not assess it, Kulkarni *et al* report ranges from 89.7–193.2 billion USD/year to reduce food waste, shift to healthier food diets and enforce land protection policies.

If such investments in the land and food sectors took place, they might imply cost reduction in the water and energy sectors for a maximum of 26 billion USD/year in the short term and 47 billion USD/year in the long term.

Taking these potential synergies into account, the overall water-energy costs that comply with achieving WEL SDGs range between 20.9–63.7 billion USD/year before 2040 and 100.7 billion USD/year for the long-term (figure 2(a)).

The spread is due to different climate assumptions, ranging from historical climate conditions to assuming a global average temperature by 2100 increase of about 2.5 °C—corresponding to radiative forcing stabilized at 6.0 W m⁻² after 2100, Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP 6.0)—and varying levels of water reliability, as explained in the Methods (van Vuuren *et al* 2011).

As we live in a world of inequalities, the paths toward achieving the SDGs differ from country to country, depending on the current level of development, access to basic services, financial capacity and exposure to climate impacts. Figure 3(b) shows the regional variability of the SDG cost increase in the water sector for the RCP 6.0 climate scenario (excluding land impacts). South-Saharan African countries and South Asian countries, including India, would require an annual average increase in investment and O&M in the energy supply and water sectors of about 30%, and West Asia and North Africa (WANAF) 15%.

3.2. Sectoral and temporal breakdown of uncertainty

Figure 4 shows the regional ranges of water and energy supply average annual investments and O&M cost variation compliant with achieving WEL SDG given by scenarios that range between ‘historical climate’ assumption, RCP 6.0, inclusion or exclusion of land-climate impacts and three levels of water reliability, as explained in Method and table S2.

Energy supply costs range from –2% to +2% variation from a non-SDG target in most regions with no noticeable differences between short- and long-term. South-Saharan Africa and South Asia are standing out as regions where providing adequate cooling demand to the population might require an increase of 5% in the supply sector only. Additional costs for demand-side implementation for the same objective are also expected and should be estimated.

Figure 3. Water infrastructure annual average Investment and O&M (AAIOM) cost increase achieving WEL SDGs before 2040. Sectoral decomposition of water investment and contribution to the specific SDG addition, scenarios noSDG-rcp6p0, SDG-wat-rcp6p0-wat, SDG-AC-rcp6p0-AC-HY, SDG-land-rcp6p0-land, SDG-rcp6p0 (a). Map showing the difference in water AAIOM between a scenario with WEL SDG targets and one without (scenario SDG-rcp6p0-noland), both with RCP 6.0 consistent climate impacts (b). Map showing the reduction in water AAIOM when only the food-waste and land conservation SDG targets are achieved, scenarios SDG-land-rcpref (c).

China shows a larger uncertainty due to climate in the long term that is twice as large as the short-term uncertainty, which indicates vulnerability to climate impacts regarding cooling needs.

Looking at the water investment and O&M cost, all regions seem to have some increase in costs, which are higher in regions that still lack access to clean water and sanitation for large shares of the population. In this case, looking at the 90th and 70th percentiles of the water availability distribution (*highrel* and *medrel* scenarios) a significant increase in SDG costs and a larger spread between historical and RCP 6.0 climate is noticeable, as shown by the bars and lines and the ‘x’ dots in figure 4(a).

South-Saharan Africa and South Asia are, also in this case, the regions with the largest maximum cost increase of around +40%, where however, RCP 6.0 scenarios consistently play the high end of the cost range. West Asia and North Africa also result in a high-end maximum +26% increase in costs. Importantly, the selected scenarios define a range of uncertainty in these results. While the solution space in Africa seems narrow, South Asia and Central Asia (mainly China) report an uncertainty range of about 30% for short-term investments, followed by WANaf with 15%. This uncertainty is an important indicator of risk for investors and planners when, for instance, climate impact might boost investment needs from +9% to +39% in South Asia. The low and high end of these ranges are delimited by a scenario with low water reliability with lower SDG costs and minor uncertainty and those with high reliability, showing higher costs and uncertainty.

Figure S1 shows the overall water and energy supply annual mean investments per region for a scenario with no climate impacts and no SDG targets. Noticeably, the energy investments are higher than those in the water sector, because of the higher complexity of most technologies. Also a few percentage points’ variations in energy investments depicted in figure 4, mean billions of USD. For instance, looking at India and Southeast Asia, the water SDG costs range between 18.5–21.5 billion USD/year, higher than for energy 1–7.8 billion USD/year. However, the absolute uncertainty range is higher for energy, resulting in 6.8 vs 3 billion USD/year in water. Even considering the highest SDG investment requirements for India, it would

result in less than 1% of the country’s GDP in 2024. As mentioned before, the most relevant model outcome is the magnitude of change and the regional and sectoral decomposition rather than the absolute investment values. The absolute investment estimates are discounted with a 5% interest rate and might be considered optimistic. Real-world cases might inflate these costs.

3.3. Overlap and linkages between SDG and climate impacts

Narrow uncertainty ranges indicate that the model finds solutions in terms of capacity expansion that are not strongly affected by impacts such as variations in precipitation, and changes in agriculture yields. On the contrary, large ranges indicate that different infrastructure portfolios are needed to reach the SDG targets

because of constraints or limitations imposed by the climate impacts. For example, we consider two scenarios with both WEL SDG targets but very different climate assumptions *SDG-rcp6p0-noland*, with scarce water availability and *SDG-rcpref-lowrel*, where renewable water resources are more abundant (see figure S6). Because of more scarce renewable surface and groundwater, some regions compensate for the need for water by increasing wastewater recycling, and desalination, or by extracting non-renewable brackish or groundwater, with a high risk of aquifer exploitation. Figure 5(b) shows the ratio of water extracted from the aforementioned non-renewable water sources and the overall basin water withdrawals. In an SDG scenario, several countries could have an untapped potential to reuse treated water. Desalination would also be a key technology, especially in East and West Asia and North Africa. Central Asia regions might pursue groundwater extraction by exploring deeper aquifers, which might become extremely expensive, as suggested by the extraction O&M cost in India for high and medium reliability scenarios in India (figure 5(a)). This phenomenon should be constrained and controlled by the local authorities.

Looking at the water cost-change composition when targeting WEL SDG in some of the regions with the highest SDG costs, O&M seems slightly higher than the investments, this is because of the long lifetime of water infrastructure, which however has running and maintenance costs (figure 5(a)).

We notice that achieving the SDG targets implies some savings in water extraction investments, both because of the withdrawal reductions from agriculture and because of water scarcity (these reductions when moving from *low* to *high*-reliability scenarios). The reliability dimension in our scenarios seems to play a stronger role compared to the inclusion of climate impact. Still, RCP6.0 records higher cost shifts than the 'no climate scenarios'. Transitioning from low to medium to high reliability (meaning a system reliable to lesser water availability) investments and O&M costs in desalination infrastructure increase drastically in China and the WANaf. In all regions, with particular emphasis on South Asia, a strong increase mainly in groundwater extraction might be critical if not well planned and regulated. Finally, SSAf is the region with the smallest changes related to climate variability and where most of the investments and O&M needs are for improving water treatment and recycling.

Climate impacts on the land sector, such as crop yields, and water availability, lead to important changes in our results (figure 5(a)). The land-system model used in this study, GLOBIOM, shows several diverging trends from a similar model we have compared to, IMAGE. Figures S3 and S4 show different results in crop yields, water use in irrigation, agricultural production and use of fertilizer when considering the RCP 6.0 climate scenario.

These differences are model-specific and might depend on assumptions that define different cost-optimal solutions to exogenous change. In particular, the GLOBIOM model shows positive direct impacts on crop yields in several regions, which leads to benefits in terms of crop productivity. In regions and crops where yields and water resources worsen with temperature increase, the model responds with strong use of fertilizer and still a reduction in water withdrawals. Such solutions seem to be different from other land models, such as IMAGE, which prioritize different dynamics.

For this reason, to build robustness on the findings of this study, we run scenarios where land climate impacts are not included (denominated with *-noland*). At the same time, we keep transparency on the large uncertainty in the land sector and invite the land modelling community to share and compare their model results.

Our results show a very large level of investment increase and uncertainty ranges in the long term, also in regions that have relatively low short-term costs, which is an aspect not much explored by the existing literature. This is because some regions will still experience population growth throughout the century, and climate impacts are likely to be perceived as stronger after 2040. Figure 4 shows that South Asia and Central Asia could have more than 30% variation in long-term costs, the WANaf and Former Soviet Union area between 10% and 15% and Asian smaller countries and Europe about 5% variation. In the SDG context, this means that planning and investment allocations are important and required not only to provide access to electricity, cooling capacity, water and sanitation by 2030 to the current population but also in sight of future population growth and climate impacts.

4. Future work & model improvements

Like any process-based model, the one used in this study has limitations in assessing sectoral investment costs. While water infrastructure costs include both supply and demand options, the model only accounts for energy supply costs—from primary resources to final energy carriers. Costs related to energy demand (e.g. households, industry, transport) and the land sector are not included, though their transformations and cross-sector implications are represented. Expanding cost coverage and incorporating countries' financial capacity is a key priority for future work and could lead to higher overall investment estimates.

As mentioned above, climate impacts on crop yields, while being an important impact factor for water demands, resulted uncertain when compared to the literature. More sensitivity runs from agriculture and land models are needed to assess the most probable outcomes under climate change.

Further work will also focus on more efficient ways of integrating impacts in models, moving from a climate scenario approach (i.e. RCP2.6 or 6.0) to integrating and emulating the impacts endogenously based on pre-processed impacts data. The representation of extreme events such as heat waves, droughts, and floods is still a major question for models with coarse temporal and spatial scales. Upcoming work will focus on increasing the temporal resolution of MESSAGEix-Nexus to capture seasonal events and use stochastic and probabilistic approaches to generate stress-test scenarios, as an improvement of the extreme scenarios considered in this work.

5. Discussion

Although the link between development and climate strategies is widely acknowledged, most studies assess SDG investment needs and climate impacts in isolation, failing to account for how climate change alters the financial requirements for achieving development goals. This study addresses that gap by examining how climate variability shapes investment demands across the water and energy sectors. Focusing on energy supply and water infrastructure investments—including cooling demand, basic water services, and environmental flow preservation—we provide estimates that can inform regional planning and development financing. Our findings emphasize the need to integrate climate adaptation into SDG investment strategies, ensuring both sustainability and resilience, particularly in vulnerable regions.

We estimate between a 10% to 30% expenditure increase in the water sector to achieve WEL SDG in water-scarce regions such as Africa, West, South and East Asia; values that lie in the low-to-average range if compared to previous work and that overall results for less than 1% of global yearly GDP (Parkinson *et al* 2019, Kulkarni *et al* 2022). The largest share in costs for developing countries is represented by the water treatment and recycling gap. Scenarios with a warmer climate (RCP 6.0) or with assumed high water reliability also have costs related to unconventional water extraction (desalination and brackish groundwater) which might weigh up to 50% of the total costs, depending on the region.

Our results also highlighted a significant heat stress increase in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa, which might require about a 5% increase in energy supply investments. In particular, in India and African countries, air conditioning uptake has been slower than in other regions, and other solutions, including nature-based solutions, might be considered by urban planners (Davis *et al* 2021).

Our findings underscore that financing mechanisms should account for climate-induced uncertainties, particularly in South and West Asia and North Africa, where investment variability could reach 30% due to climate and water reliability uncertainties. The uncertainty in water investments is mostly driven by water reliability uncertainty, with scenarios testing the first decile (90th percentile scenario) of the runoff and groundwater recharge distribution showing larger SDG-related costs and larger variation than scenarios that consider the average of the distributions (*highrel* vs *lowrel*). Climate forcing differences, from historical climate to RCP 6.0 in this work, are a clear but minor driver of the uncertainty, especially in the Asia regions. Land impacts and crop yield changes are also an important source of uncertainty which requires more detailed exploration in future analyses.

This study shows that investment requirements increase over time, particularly after 2040, as climate impacts intensify and the population grows. This is often overlooked in existing studies, which focus on short-term SDG costs. We show that Investments and O&M costs related to water access and security targets are largely dependent on climate change in the long-term time horizon (between 2040 and 2100) when climate impacts are likely to hit stronger. We evaluate that all regions will need to sustain similar, if not higher yearly expenditure in water infrastructure to maintain the SDG standards. Climate impacts might define, also for less-water-stressed regions, higher uncertainty in long-term costs than in the short-term. The direct implication of these results is that planning and development funding mechanisms should be responsive to regional vulnerabilities and prepared to address increased investment needs in the long term.

Our insights on the long-term time horizon will hopefully pave the way for more research on water resilience to climate change to achieve water access and quality targets. Since the global discussions and agreements (i.e. Conferences of the Parties) are increasingly focusing on adaptation and the interlinkages with sustainable development, this study should also help navigate the uncertainty in the costs of adopting alternative solutions.

It should be noted that extreme climate events that are reported to increase with global average temperatures, such as floods and drought, also affect the investment in the water sector (Pourzand and Noy 2022, Kim *et al* 2023). Both costs for building systems resilient to extreme events and damages from catastrophic hazards are not fully accounted for in this study because of the small spatial and temporal scale they manifest and will likely become an important part of the expenditure in the future.

A key insight from this study is the economic benefits in the water sector when achieving nutrition policies together with food waste policies (Pham-Truffert *et al* 2020). Other papers have highlighted how food waste, if considered a virtual country, would rank 9th globally in blue water consumption, which means large savings are possible, especially by reducing consumption losses (Coudard *et al* 2021). Food waste reduction and improved nutrition (with an overall decline in meat consumption) imply water withdrawal reduction, are in line with studies using other IAMs (Doelman *et al* 2022). Our contribution adds an estimate of the reduction in investment and O&M expenditure related to reductions in water withdrawals. This might account for a maximum of 26.1 billion USD/year in reduction in the water sector, on average one-seventh of the estimated expenditure for implementing the food and land policies (Kulkarni *et al* 2022), whilst reducing vulnerability to water stress. Regionally the benefits are well distributed across regions and

particularly high for South Asia (i.e. India). This investment "vacuum" could also be seen as an opportunity to plan new investments in land use or water distribution and irrigation efficiency improvement.

This demonstrates the economic benefits of integrated WEL policies and highlights opportunities to optimize financing across sectors. Still, we foresee further improvements in our modelling framework to be able to internalize the assessment of investments and other costs in the land-food system model to carry out integrated cost comparisons.

6. Policy implications and conclusions

Our findings underscore the need for more coherent and adaptive financing mechanisms that integrate climate adaptation into SDG investment strategies. Given the significant role of climate change in shaping development costs and long-term resilience, funding schemes for development and adaptation should be better aligned to maximize efficiency and impact. For example, mechanisms like the Global Environment Facility, which operates under UNDP, and the Adaptation Fund, established under the UNFCCC, should work in synergy rather than in parallel, ensuring that financial resources are allocated effectively across sectors and regions.

For regions such as Africa and South Asia, where climate impacts and investment uncertainties are particularly high, policymakers must carefully prioritize spending in key sectors like water access, treatment, and heat stress adaptation. Strengthening cross-sectoral synergies is equally important. In particular, policies aimed at improving food security and reducing food waste in high-income countries could alleviate water stress and reduce the overall financial burden of water sector investments. By addressing inefficiencies in resource use, these policies can contribute to cost savings and make adaptation investments more sustainable in the long run.

Looking ahead, long-term financial strategies must recognize that investment needs will likely continue to rise beyond 2030 due to population growth and increasing climate impacts. While SDG targets provide a crucial benchmark, the financial demands of climate adaptation may surpass development-related costs, particularly in rapidly urbanizing countries like China, where rising water and energy demands will be key drivers of future expenditures. Ensuring that investment frameworks account for these evolving challenges will be essential in building resilient, climate-adaptive infrastructure that can sustain economic and social development throughout the century.

Beyond offering policy-relevant insights, this manuscript highlights advances in representing multi-sector biophysical impacts in IAMs and identifies key areas for further model development.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at the following URL/DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7687577>.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Author contributions

AV is responsible for all stages from model co-development, to data and result analysis, paper conceptualization, writing and creation of the figures. M A was involved in methodology and software development, paper conceptualization and paper review. E B paper conceptualization, supervision, feedback and paper review. V K and K R funding acquisition, paper conceptualization, supervision, feedback.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

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Code references

The model development done to run the scenarios in this article is described in (Awais *et al* 2024). The code and documentation are available on the MESSAGEix public Github page (<https://github.com/iiasa/messageix-models>) and documentation (<https://docs.messageix.org/projects/models/en/latest/water/index.html>).

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